

to identify local BPH biotypes. Pelita I/1, IR26, IR36, IR42, IR46, IR56, and Bahbolon were transplanted in each plot with three replications on 6 Aug.

BPH infested the plots soon after transplanting. There were bimodal population peaks at 4-5 and 7-8 wk, which corresponded to the maximum nymphal stages of the first and second generations. Between population peaks, brachypterous females emerged. Their population peaked at 6 wk. The BPH population declined sharply after 10 wk, probably because of drought. No hopperburn developed.

However, statistically significant differences in BPH densities were recorded among the rice varieties at six insect development stages. Population was significantly higher on IR42 and the susceptible check Pelita I/1 (see table). Populations were particularly low on IR46, IR56, and Bahbolon. Interestingly,

Comparison of population density of the BPH on 6 different rice varieties at 6 different stages in the rice garden in Deli Serdang, North Sumatra, 1983.^a

Variety	Resistance gene	Insects/hill					
		M-female (2 wk)	F ₁ S-nymph (4 wk)	F ₁ L-nymph (5 wk)	B-female (6 wk)	F ₂ S-nymph (7-8 wk)	F ₂ L-nymph (8-9 wk)
Pelita I/1	None	2.4 ab	252 a	67 a	4.3 a	60 a	6.0 a
IR42	<i>bph 2</i>	3.3 a	202 a	70 a	4.3 a	83 a	7.3 a
IR36	<i>bph 2</i>	1.5 bc	81 b	20 b	0.9 ab	27 b	1.7 b
IR26	<i>Bph 1</i>	1.1 bc	16 bc	7 b	0.4 b	7 bc	0.1 b
IR56	<i>Bph 3</i>	1.3 bc	20 bc	5 b	0.2 b	0.2 c	0.2 b
IR46	<i>Bph 1</i>	1.0 bc	3 c	4 b	0.1 b	0.3 c	0.2 b
Bahbolon	<i>Bph 3</i>	0.4 c	1 c	1 b	0.02 b	0.1 c	0.1 b

^aValues followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level. F₁ = first generation, F₂ = second generation, M-female = macropterous adult female, B-female = brachypterous adult female, S-nymph = 1st- to 3d-instar nymphs, L-nymph = 4th- to 5th-instar nymphs. Time in parentheses indicates weeks after transplanting.

IR26, which had been attacked by BPH biotype 2, showed good resistance. Results indicated that the local BPH population was biotype 3, adapted to IR42, which corresponded with laboratory identification of locally

collected BPH. The rice garden method is recommended as a simple but highly practical method of monitoring BPH biotype shifts, and forecasting BPH population surge and development of other insect pests and diseases. □

Relationship between biochemical characteristics of rice and establishment of yellow stem borer (YSB) larvae

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We conducted greenhouse experiments to determine the ability of YSB larvae to establish themselves on rice accessions with selected biochemical characteristics.

Twenty-day-old seedlings of 6 accessions (see table) and the susceptible check Jaya were transplanted 1/hill in 10-cm earthen pots in a 90- × 60- × 5-cm galvanized iron tray filled with water. Fifty days after seeding, one freshly hatched larva was released on each tiller.

Larval establishment and biochemical characteristics of selected rice accessions, Coimbatore, India.

Accession	Larval establishment (%)	Leaf sheath		Stem		
		Total N (%)	Crude silica (%)	Crude silica (%)	Lignin (mg/g)	Cellulose (mg/g)
W1263	9	3.6	4.8	11.40	417	671
Co 18	20	2.4	2.3	9.87	532	608
IR13641-4	23	5.0	0.6	12.12	279	737
IR13639-39	45	4.9	1.4	5.85	143	887
Sornavazhai	45	3.1	3.7	3.17	583	566
Jaya	50	3.1	1.7	6.51	464	710

Each accession was in 3 replications of 10 hills/replication.

Ten days after larvae were released, single accessions were pulled and the leaf sheath and lumen were carefully observed to determine the presence and position of the larvae. Percent larval establishment was calculated based on larval recovery.

The leaf sheaths and stems of accessions were analyzed for total N, crude silica, lignin, and cellulose.

Larval establishment was lowest in W1263, followed by Co 18 and IR13641-4 (see table). It was highest in susceptible Jaya. Only crude silica content was significantly related to percent larval establishment. The resistant accessions had more silica than other accessions in their stems. □

Inhibitory effects of insecticides on entomogenous fungi *Metarrhizium anisopliae* and *Beauveria bassiana*

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M. anisopliae and *B. bassiana* are the most commonly isolated entomogenous fungi from field-collected brown planthopper (BPH) in the Philippines. Because BPH resurgence is linked with insecticide application, it may be that insecticides applied to control BPH also inhibit natural enemies of BPH. We evaluated the effect of insecticides recommended for BPH control and BPH resurgence-causing insecticides on the germination of *M. anisopliae* and *B. bassiana* spores.

Insecticide was mixed into the culture media before planting, or was surface-applied on hardened media. All insecticides significantly reduced spore germination of both fungi (see table). *M. anisopliae* was more sensitive to insecti-

Effect of insecticides on *M. anisopliae* and *B. bassiana* spore germination, IRRI, 1983.

Insecticide	Spore germination ^a (%)			
	Insecticide mixed with media ^b		Insecticide on media surface ^c	
	<i>M. anisopliae</i>	<i>B. bassiana</i>	<i>M. anisopliae</i>	<i>B. bassiana</i>
	<i>Recommended for BPH control^d</i>			
Monocrotophos	0 c	32 b	72 b	95 b
BPMC	1 b	2 c	36 d	36 d
Carbosulfan	0 c	0 d	66 c	68 c
Azinphos ethyl + BPMC	0 c	0 d	28 e	68 c
No insecticide	99 a	100 a	99 a	100 a
Insecticide mean	0	9	51	67
	<i>Causing BPH resurgence^e</i>			
Azinphos ethyl	20 d	71 c	16 d	77 c
Deltamethrin	56 c	90 b	81 b	89 b
Methyl parathion	0 e	6 e	15 d	72 d
MIPC	66 b	38 d	75 c	67 e
No insecticide	99 a	100 a	99 a	100 a
Insecticide mean	36	51	47	77

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. 300 random spores counted 24 h after insecticide application. ^bInsecticide mixed with the culture media at 40-45°C, then plated. Fungal spore suspension (0.3 ml/petri dish) was spread on the cooled and hardened media. ^cInsecticides and fungi spores were mixed together in suspension and 0.3 ml/petri dish was spread on top of the hardened culture media. ^dAt the national recommended rate of 0.75 kg ai/ha. ^eAt the minimal rate that causes resurgence (0.50 kg ai/ha, except deltamethrin at 0.025 kg ai/ha).

Influence of flooding, fertilizer, and plant spacing on insect pest incidence

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We studied the influence of cultural methods on reducing insect pest incidence in rice in 1981 kuruvai.

Continuous flooding and alternate flooding and draining; 15- × 10-cm, 20-

× 10-cm, and 30- × 10-cm spacing (water regimes and spacings were main plots); 50, 100, and 150 kg N/ha; and 42 and 83 kg K/ha (N and K treatments were sub-plots) were tested in a split-plot design with 3 replications. TKM9 was planted in 1 6-m² plots. Tillers and silvershoots were counted in 19 randomly chosen hills/plot 30 and 50 d after transplanting (DT). Populations of green leafhopper (GLH) and brown planthopper (BPH), and whorl maggot (WM) damaged leaves on 10 hills/

Insect population and grain yield as determined by cultural practice, Aduthurai, India.^a

Treatment	GLH/10 hills	BPH/10 hills	WM (% damaged leaves)	GM (% silvershoots)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Water management</i>					
Continuous flooding	19 b	9 b	7 b	2a	5.6 a
Alternate flooding and draining	13 a	4a	4a	3 b	4.9 b
<i>Spacing</i>					
15 × 10 cm	13 a	6	5	3	5.0
20 × 10 cm	18 b	6	6	2	5.2
30 × 10 cm	18 b	6	5	3	5.5
<i>N level</i>					
50 kg/ha	15 a	3a	5	2	4.8 b
100 kg/ha	16 a	7 b	5	2	5.2 b
150 kg/ha	18 b	8 c	5	3	5.7 a
<i>K level</i>					
42 kg/ha	17	6	5	2	5.2
83 kg/ha	16	6	5	3	5.3

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

cides. Recommended insecticides reduced spore germination more than resurgence-causing insecticides did, probably because a higher dosage of the recommended insecticide was applied.

Because both types of insecticides greatly inhibited spore germination of both fungi, it is unlikely that insecticides cause resurgence by counteracting the beneficial effect of entomogenous fungi. Among the BPH resurgence-causing insecticides, deltamethrin, the most powerful, had the weakest effect on spore germination. Only methyl parathion, the second most powerful BPH resurgence-causing insecticide, greatly reduced spore germination. □

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plot were counted 20, 45, and 70 DT. Grain yield was recorded.

Alternate flooding and draining significantly reduced GLH and BPH populations and WM damage. The 10- × 15-cm spacing reduced GLH numbers (see table). The BPH population increased with N application. K did not influence insect damage or grain yield. Increased gall midge (GM) incidence in plots with intermittent flooding may have been caused by a change in microclimate, and yield reduction may have been caused by hardening of the soil. □

Effect of organophosphatic insecticides on the yellow stem borer (YSB) eggs and parasites

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Insecticides used in rice fields often kill nontarget insect species. We studied the effect of seven insecticides on YSB eggs and egg parasite *Telenomus dignoides* Nixon (Hymenoptera, Scelionidae). Field